

Soil engineering properties and stabilization of Purulia soil by chemical treatment (with calcium salts)

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The soil index and engineering properties like the specific gravity, grain-size, liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), compaction characteristics, compression index (C_c), etc. of Purulia soils were studied. The soil characteristics and their engineering properties (stabilization) can be considerably improved and strengthened through addition of chemicals. A systematic investigation on soil stabilization by CaCl₂ and Ca(OH)₂ to a Purulia soil was carried out. The effect of added chemicals on the engineering properties was examined to derive useful inferences on stabilization of the given soils by chemicals. Efforts have been made to offer physico-chemical explanation on soil stabilization.

The River Research Institute, West Bengal, is primarily concerned with the studies on the mechanical properties of soils particularly useful for the construction of sluices, dams, bridges, pump houses and other construction purposes in different parts of West Bengal. Some investigations are performed to study the causes of river bank failures.

In most cases, penetration tests are done at the site to get the consistency/relative density of cohesive/non-cohesive soils. Undisturbed samples are collected near the site (spot) from auger holes or by using the Dutch cone penetration apparatus. The soil samples collected are subjected to different laboratory tests like grain size analysis, specific gravity, Atterberg limits, etc. to determine index and assess engineering properties to understand the nature and type of the soil profile for the safe construction of substructures.

Dedalal *et al.*¹ reported the results of dynamic cone penetration tests at the dam sites in the fringe areas of the Chhotonagpur highlands and Western margins of Rarh.

Dedalal² also reported the results of a continuous record of the consistency/relative density, grain size of the subsoils in the alluvial region of West Bengal by a Dutch cone penetrometer.

Investigations on soil engineering properties have been performed extensively in the Western and other parts of world³⁻¹⁰ in connection with various construction projects.

However, it is well known that the soil characteristics and their engineering properties can be considerably strengthened by addition of chemicals known as stabilization. Stabilization of soils can be achieved by various methods for the modification and improvement of the properties of soils for engineering purposes¹¹⁻¹³.

Lime was extensively used to modify the engineering properties of fine grained soils. Mitchel and Hooper¹⁴ emphasize that the strength of soil-lime mixtures is dependent on many variables such as soil type, lime content, type of lime, curing time and method (temperature and water availability), water content, unit weight and time elapsed between mixing and compaction. In a study of lime reactivity of Illinois soils, Thompson¹⁵ found that the lime reactivity i.e. the maximum increase of shear strength of a clay by lime addition is higher in soils of poorly drained areas having higher pH. Organic carbon retards lime soil reaction and calcareous soils give better reactivity. Sabry and Parcher¹⁶ observed that compaction at moisture contents above optimum produces very beneficial effects on the soil strength. Clough, Kuck and Kasali¹⁷ reported the behaviour of silicate stabilized sands. It is a procedure commonly used in Europe and Japan to minimize movements around shallow tunnels in urban area.

Stabilization of soils can be considered to be widely used procedure in developed countries but such studies are relatively few in India. The importance of such studies, however, has attracted attention in recent years.

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Fig. 1. Particle size distribution curve of Purulia clay.

Chakraborty *et al.*¹⁸ conducted a study on the stabilization of a Bankura clay mixed with varying percentage of lime. The reduction in the values of LL and PI was noted and changes in other engineering properties were observed. Results of different tests conducted on a Birbhum clay stabilized with lime and fly ash were reported by Dedalal and Nath¹². A study on the leaching of lime from lime - fly ash stabilized soils has been conducted by APERL, Hyderabad²⁰. Sivapulliah, Sridharan and Ramesh²¹ studied the effect of the presence of sulphate in a lime stabilized black cotton soil and observed negative effect of sulphate on cement stabilized soils.

Fig. 2. Standard proctor compaction (test results).

The role of dolomitic impurity on the properties of lime treated soils had been studied by Sivapulliah *et al.*²². (Most of the studies are related to soil stabilization and change in their engineering properties with the addition of suitable chemicals). Moreover, contaminants from diverse sources like land disposal of solid wastes, sewage disposal on land, agricultural, industrial and mining activities etc. may ingress into soils and affect their overall behaviour. Gupta and Singh¹⁶ have reviewed the consequences of contaminants and their interactions in details.

Fig. 3. Stress-strain plots of different soil samples (compacted at or near proctor values).

Though the investigations on the engineering properties of soils of West Bengal have been carried out to some extent, detailed studies on soil stabilization by different added chemicals have not been studied (only lime and fly ash stabilization at o.m.c. have been studied on some soils of West Bengal^{18,19,24}). A systematic investigation on soil stabilization by added chemicals e.g. CaCl_2 , $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ etc. appears useful and desirable. This led us to investigate the effect of controlled chemical treatment on a Purulia soil.

The objective of the present investigation is to study the effect of controlled chemical treatment to a Purulia soil to improve and strengthen the soil characteristics and the engineering properties what is known as stabilization. The extent of stabilization of the Purulia soil with chemicals like CaCl_2 , $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ can be understood from the study of different engineering properties. It is to be

Fig. 4. $e - \log p$ plots of different soil samples compacted at or near proctor values.

Fig. 5. $e - \log p$ plots of different soil samples consolidated from LL state.

noted that stabilization has greater importance for the construction purposes.

The results of the investigations are presented in this communication.

Experimental

The silty clay used in the present investigation was collected from a proposed dam site in Purulia district (Western region). Disturbed soil sample was collected near the site from a dug pit.

The sample collected was subjected to different laboratory tests to determine the specific gravity, grain size analy-

Fig. 6. Stress-strain plots of soil samples (sedimented from LL state under 48 kg/cm^2).

sis, liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), cation exchange capacity (CEC), compaction, compression index (C_c), undrained shear strength (C_u), Atterberg limits, permeability compaction characteristics, compression index (C_c) and undrained shear strength (C_u). Atterberg limits, permeability, compaction, compression and undrained shear tests of the chemically treated soils were undertaken. Loss in concentrations of added chemicals during consolidation/sedimentation were also ascertained.

Preparation of sample for different mechanical tests :

(a) *Sedimentation in laboratory :*

In nature a soil deposit gets consolidated due to its own weight and the soil profile takes many many years to gain shape in the present form. But in different clay model studies in the laboratory, sedimentation of clayey soil is done to have a controlled deposit. Clay is sedimented from liquid limit state (or higher moisture content) under a dead weight or hydraulic load. Natural environments are tough to be simulated in the laboratory. A natural clay possesses a flocculated structure but a sedimented clay usually develops a dispersed structure rather than a flocculated structure.

In the present study, the soil slurry with moisture content at or near liquid limit was put in sedimentation tank made of Perspex. The dimensions of the tank were 8.86 cm dia, 16.6 cm length. Drainage arrangements were there both at the top and the bottom. Dead weights were gradually placed on the top of the loading ram. The total sedimentation load was 29.6 kg with intensity 0.48 kg/cm^2 . 48 h was allowed for consolidation. The soil samples for shear and permeability tests were properly dressed after collecting the samples by extraction with cutters within the soil column. For permeability measurements sample sizes were 3" (dia) $\times$ 1" (thickness) and for shear stress measurements sample sizes were 3.5 cm (dia) $\times$ 5.6 cm (length), i.e. $L/D = 1.6$.

(b) Atterberg limit test :

Aqueous solution/suspension of different chemical additives at different concentrations were added to oven dried soil (150 g) with vigorous shaking and mixing. The soil mass, kept in humid chamber for 7 days for maturing/curing, was subjected to Atterberg's limits tests^{3,11}.

(c) Shear and permeability test :

The aqueous solution/suspension of salts at different concentrations were added to oven dried soil maintaining the moisture content at or near liquid limit. The chemically treated soil samples were kept 7 days for maturing. The samples in the form of slurry were subjected to sedimentation process under load intensity 0.48 kg/cm² in a sedimentation tank as discussed earlier and then the soil mass was subjected to shear and permeability test^{3,11}.

(d) Consolidation test :

The oven dried soil samples (100 g) were mixed with the aqueous solutions/suspensions of salts at various concentrations and water was then added to maintain liquid limit moisture content. The samples were kept 7 days for maturing/curing in humid chamber. The soil slurry was then subjected to consolidation test^{3,11}.

(e) Compaction test :

About 2 kg of oven dried soil was mixed with salts at different concentrations. Requisite amount of water was added to soil mixture and kept for 7 days in a humid chamber. The soil mass was then subjected to compaction test^{3,11}.

Consolidation, shear and permeability tests were also done at optimum moisture content (o.m.c.) using only Ca(OH)₂.

The soils samples were subjected to consolidation/sedimentation tests using aqueous suspensions (blank) and salt solutions (at different concentrations). Loss of concentration of salt solutions (at different concentrations) were determined from the difference in the concentrations of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions in leached solutions from the experimental and blank solutions. The concentrations of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions were determined using a Systronics Digital flame photometer²⁵ (model 125). Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions were estimated using EDTA in the usual way²⁵.

Results and discussion

The silty clay (having clay content 42.2%) used, was collected from a proposed dam site in Purulia district (Western region). It is residual in origin¹. The tract is well drained i.e. the soil has been formed in leaching and oxidis-

ing environments⁸. It is expected that the soil is composed of base unsaturated type having little or no alluvial experience and the soil has lower degree of activity (Table 1). The Purulia soil is known to be composed of mostly kaolinite^{1,8}. Illite may be present to some extent. The index properties are given in Table 1. Particle sizes are shown in the size distribution curve (Fig. 1). From the stabilization of Purulia soil of lower activity it may be inferred that the soils of other regions (specially southern region) will react better with chemicals leading to greater stabilization.

(A) Atterberg limit values^{5-7,18,21,22,26} :

Liquid limit of Purulia soil is 48.5 and plastic limit and plasticity index, (LL-PL), values are 20.5 and 28 respectively (Table 2). Results of Atterberg limit values of some of the chemically treated soil samples cured for 7 days have been given in Table 2.

Table 1. Index properties of Purulia clay

(1) Soil description	: Yellowish brown loamy clay	
(2) Liquid limit (LL)	: 48.5%	
(3) Plastic limit (PL)	: 20.5%	
(4) Plasticity index (PI)	: 28.0% (LL-PL)	
(5) Clay content (<0.002 mm)	: 42.2%	
(6) Activity $\left(\frac{PI}{Clay\%}\right) = \frac{28}{42.2} = 0.66$		
(7) Sp. gravity (G)	: ~2.72	
(8) Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	: ~12.81 me/100 g	
(9) Differential free swell index = 20%		
(10) Particle size distribution :		
Sand% (0.06-2)	Silt% (0.002-0.06)	Clay% (below 0.002)
mm	mm	mm
22.0	35.8	42.2
(11) C _c Compression index of the clay (initial stage being LL) = 0.335		
(12) C _u Undrained shear strength, kg/cm ² of clay sedimented (initial stage being LL) under 0.48 kg/cm ² = 0.076 kg/cm ² .		
$\frac{C_u}{p} = \frac{0.076}{0.48} = 0.16$		

Table 2. Atterberg's limits of the soil with and without chemical additives

Sl. no.	Soil details	Liquid limit (LL)	Plastic limit (PL)	Plasticity index (PI) (LL-PL)
1.	Clay blank (Purulia soil)	48.5	20.5	28.0
2.	Soil + 0.8% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	45.5	19.5	26.0
3.	Soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	44.3	19.3	25.0
4.	Soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	43.6	20.6	23.0
5.	Soil + 0.8% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	42.8	21.8	21.0
6.	Soil + 1% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	42.5	21.5	21.0
7.	Soil + 2% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	43.5	-	-
8.	Soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	47.5	21.5	26.0
9.	Soil + 1% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	45.8	24.8	21.0
10.	Soil + 2% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	49.0	30.0	19.0
11.	Soil + 0.1% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	44.0	20.0	24.0
12.	Soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	43.0	20.0	23.0
13.	Soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	42.5	20.7	21.8

In the soils treated with Ca^{2+} (as CaCl_2), the effect of salt addition is lowering of LL. However with very high salt concentration this tendency is stopped. The PL values are slightly less with lower salt concentration but with higher concentration it is even more than the values of the blank soil. The tendency of lowering of plasticity range i.e. PI values is evident.

With addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, the lowering effect is pronounced in LL values but the PL values are found unaffected. PI values show a lowering tendency. But in $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ treated soils, the effect of salt addition is less in the case of LL values compared to other types of salt treated soils. At higher concentration the value has been found to be increased. The PL values are more than that of the blank soil and the PI values are found to have decreased gradually with higher concentrations of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

In a soil suspension, tendency of flocculation is the result of increase of net attractive force and it may be caused by increasing ion concentration, ion valency etc. or by decreasing pH, size of hydrated ion, anion adsorption, dielectric constant etc.⁶.

Salt addition normally causes depression of double layer. The result is that less amount of water is immobilized by the soil particles and hence it is expected that less water is required to reach the liquid limit state. The greater the salt concentration the greater is the effect till the electrical capacity of the surface charges of the clay particles is satisfied. Then the particles with less thick double layer interact and the flocculation phenomenon dominates and more water is required to reach the liquid limit state. This is possibly the cause of lowering of LL upto a maximum salt concentration beyond which the LL once again tends to increase.

The higher valency of a cation causes greater double layer depression compared to a lower valency cation. This may be the cause of slightly greater effect with CaCl_2 . Anion adsorption on the edges of clay particle has some contribution on the double layer size. So anion may be another factor affecting the changes in Atterberg limit values. The decrease in pH causes flocculation, but with the use of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, pH is increased and at the same time there is the effect of Ca^{2+} addition. These opposing factors may contribute to the less effect on limit values due to addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

The effect on PL is slightly erratic, either the values are same or slightly reduced or the values gradually increase with the concentration of salts. The values of plasticity index i.e. the range over which the soil remains plastic is in a decreasing mode with the higher salt concentration. How-

ever, the present test programme is carried out with limited concentrations of salts only. The Purulia clay is expected to be a mixture mainly of kaolinite and illite and the activity value is rather poor

$$\bar{A} = \frac{P.I}{\text{clay}\%} = \frac{28}{42.2} = 0.66$$

Unlike montmorillonite (which has a very high specific surface) kaolinite has less surface area. So the magnitude of variations in the values of Atterberg limits are not high.

It may be inferred that the effects due to addition of salts on the Atterberg limits are mainly dependent on the clay (mineral, amount) and the salts (type i.e. cation, anion concentrations) and other factors like period of curing etc.

(B) Standard proctor compaction test^{18,19} :

The test results have been given in Fig. 2. The addition of slaked lime, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ has made the soil friable. The dry density versus moisture content plot show that the maximum dry density has been reduced to some extent and the optimum moisture content has been increased slightly.

High salt concentration has caused depression of double layer, but more water has been required for lubrication among the particles to get slipped and come closer by the compactive effort.

(C) Permeability test^{15,25} :

The results of the constant head permeability test on the sedimented samples have been presented in Table 3. The permeability coefficient of soils is a function of various factors and the test is less reproducible than the tests of index properties like Atterberg limits etc. However, the two samples of the sedimented Purulia clay have given almost identical values, the average being, 1.9×10^{-7} cm/s meaning that the soil is impermeable. The result is consistent with the clay percentage of this soil.

Table 3. Permeability test results of the sedimented soil

Sample no.	Mixture detail	Permeability coefficient (cm/s)(K) at 27°C
P-001	Clay blank (Purulia soil)	0.18×10^{-6}
		Avg. 0.19×10^{-6}
P-002	Clay blank (do)	0.20×10^{-6}
P-111	0.2% Ca^{2+} (as CaCl_2) + Purulia soil	4.40×10^{-6}
P-121	0.4% Ca^{2+} (as CaCl_2) + Purulia soil	0.56×10^{-6}
P-131	1% Ca^{2+} (as CaCl_2) + Purulia soil	2.64×10^{-6}
P-311	0.2% Ca^{2+} [as $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$] + Purulia soil	0.25×10^{-6}

The addition of Ca^{2+} (as CaCl_2) in the soil has improved the permeability value to some extent. But the results did not produce any correlation of the increase with the salt concentration. The soil added with Ca^{2+} [as $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$] has shown almost similar value of permeability compared to that of the blank soil.

Table 4. Results of the unconfined compression test on the compacted stabilized soil

Sample details	Sample no.	C_u kg/cm ²	E^* kg/cm ²	Failure strain ϵ_f %	Moisture content (%)	Dry density g/cc	e_0
Purulia soil (blank)	SC-001	1.232	76.85	4.7	17.8	1.680	0.62
Soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	SC-321	1.498	103.53	3.8	18.8	1.657	0.64

SC stands for shear test of compacted soil.
* Secant modulus at 1/2 the failure load intensity.

The inference that calcium added soil is friable, more permeable and aerated conforms to the general view of the agronomists in this matter. Actually calcium causes agglomeration and flocculation. As calcium addition results in lowering of double layer thickness, less quantity of water is immobilised by the clay particles causing less hindrance to the free flow of water through the pores. But the addition of Ca(OH)₂ elevates pH that results in deflocculating tendency. The resultant of the simultaneously occurring two opposing phenomena possibly is the cause of no significant change in value of permeability with addition of Ca(OH)₂.

Table 5. Results of the consolidation test of the compacted soil from initial state as optimum moisture content (o.m.c.)

Soil details	Sample no.	Moisture content (%)	e_0	$e_0 - e_{6.4}$	C_c at stage-1*	C_c at stage-2**
Purulia soil (blank)	CC-001	16.8	0.61	0.18	0.02	0.25
Soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	CC-321	17.8	0.63	0.17	0.03	0.22

* Stage-1 = lower load, ** Stage-2 = higher load.
CC stands for consolidation test of compacted soil.

The leaching in the process of sedimentation of salt added soil has caused lowering of concentration of additives (Table 8) from its initial value. The leaching is more pronounced in Ca²⁺ added soils. The flow of water in the permeability test has probably lessened the concentration further. But the extent of permeability or the effect of permeability on test results can not be assessed at this stage with the limited data available.

(D) Discussion on shear and consolidation test results^{9,10,15,16,19,24,25,27,28};

(i) *Compacted soil [Tables 4 and 5, Figs. 3 and 4] :*

Usually the chemical additives like slaked lime etc. are used in clayey soils having high surface activities to improve different engineering properties. Here also the Purulia clayey soil added with Ca(OH)₂ has shown improvement in undrained shear strength, C_u , when compacted at the proctor values. Fig. 3 depicts typical stress-

strain plots of some tested specimens. The secant modulus at half the failure stress (Fig. 3) has also increased and the failure has occurred at lower strain i.e. the soil has become stronger, stiffer, but brittle. The result of the consolidation tests have been plotted in Fig. 4. The compression index value, C_c , of the stabilized soil has been decreased marginally at higher loads (stage 2). (Fig. 4).

(ii) *Sedimented soil :*

In contrast with the above observations on the compacted soils the results of the sedimented soils with the chemical additives have not shown clear indication of improvement of some engineering properties. The probable causes are : (i) less reproducible test methods, (ii) different phenomena acting simultaneously nullifying individual effects, (iii) low activity of the original clayey soil etc.

Table 6. Results of the consolidation test of the stabilized soil from initial state as liquid limit

Soil details	Sample no.	Moisture content (%)	e_0	$e_0 - e_{6.4}$	$e_{0.48}$ (from $C_c - \log p$ curve)	C_c at stage-1	C_c at stage-2
Purulia soil (blank)	C-001	47.0	1.28	0.70	0.96	0.31	0.35
	C-002	47.0	1.28	0.70	0.96	0.31	0.34
Purulia soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	C-111	43.5	1.18	0.68	0.87	0.32	0.34
Purulia soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	C-121	43.4	1.19	0.65	0.93	0.32	0.36
Purulia soil + 1% Ca ²⁺ (as CaCl ₂)	C-131	43.9	1.22	0.77	0.85	0.35	0.37
Purulia soil + 0.1% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	C-201	41.9	1.23	0.64	0.95	0.32	0.34
Soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	C-211	42.5	1.18	0.71	0.84	0.255	0.33
Soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	C-221	45.6	1.30	0.74	0.99	0.38	0.41
Purulia soil + 0.2% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	C-311	44.6	1.17	0.68	0.89	0.34	0.38
Purulia soil + 0.4% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	C-321	46.6	1.29	0.70	0.97	0.30	0.375
Purulia soil + 1% Ca ²⁺ [Ca(OH) ₂]	C-331	45.6	1.28	0.67	1.03	0.31	0.40

Except Purulia soil all other data of stabilized soils are average of different specimen.
C Stands for consolidation.
Stage-1 = lower load, Stage-2 = higher load.

Consolidation test :

The results of the consolidation tests have been presented in Table 6. Fig. 5 (A, B) show the typical $e - \log p$ curves of some specimens.

In some of the tests the C_c value at lower load range (stage 1) has been found slightly less than that at higher load range (stage 2). Attempts were made : (i) to lessen the wall friction of the consolidation mould by using silicon grease and (ii) to expel entrapped air in the soil slurry by tapping, still probably these could not be achieved fully. These may be among the causes of different values of C_c at different load ranges. The values of C_c (stage 2) of all soil samples have been found to range from 0.305 to 0.410 and the values of individual specimens also vary e.g. the C_c of the blank soil i.e. Purulia clay has been found to range from 0.305 to 0.35.

Table 7. Loss of chemical additives during the process of sedimentation/consolidation

Soil details	Initial conc. (before consolidation at LL state)	Final conc. (obtained within the sedimented soil mass after complete consolidation)
Soil + 0.4% Ca^{2+} [$Ca(OH)_2$]	0.4% Ca^{2+}	0.159% Ca^{2+}
Soil + 1% Ca^{2+} [$Ca(OH)_2$]	1% Ca^{2+}	0.729% Ca^{2+}
Soil + 0.2% Ca^{2+} [$CaCl_2$]	0.2% Ca^{2+}	0.115% Ca^{2+}
Soil + 0.4% Ca^{2+} [$CaCl_2$]	0.4% Ca^{2+}	0.182% Ca^{2+}
Soil + 1% Ca^{2+} [$CaCl_2$]	1.0% Ca^{2+}	0.570% Ca^{2+}

Overall speaking, the C_c values have been found to increase with addition of different chemicals. It is astonishing as usually more the liquid limit is, more is the C_c and with admixture the values of LL have been decreased, in general. Again, the change in void ratio from the initial stage (e_0) to that at the highest load of 6.4 kg/cm^2 ($e_{6.4}$) i.e. ($e_0 - e_{6.4}$) has been found less in most cases in the chemically treated soils than in the blank Purulia soil. It simply indicates the higher rate of change of e at the higher load range.

Addition of higher concentration of calcium chloride has increased slightly the value of C_c , while with calcium nitrate additive the C_c is nearly the same at low concentration, but at higher concentration it is higher. Similar observation is found with $Ca(OH)_2$ addition.

In one set of observation (Table 7) it has been found that with sedimentation or consolidation the concentration of additives has been reduced indicating that some of the additives adsorbed loosely on the particle surfaces come out with the drained pore water under the increased load. Under each load increment the concentration is reduced, the soil at higher load is no more the same soil at lower load unlike the case of the blank soil. In practice, it has been noticed that gradual leaching by weathering deteriorates certain engineering properties of the soils stabilized with slaked lime etc.

The behavior of soil-water system is dependent on clay content, clay mineralogy, concentration of electrolyte in pore water, stress history etc. The extent of double layer is a function of clay mineralogy, electrolyte in pore water etc. So among the causes of higher C_c values of the stabilised soils at higher loads, (despite lower moulding moisture content or e_0) the change in electrolyte concentrations with the process of consolidation at different loads may be a major one.

As the soil particles are negatively charged at surfaces and positively charged at edges (possibly), the nature of cations (of the chemical additives) has some influences, at the same time that of the anions also has some effect, though no

Table 8. Results of the unconfined compression tests on the sedimented stabilized soil

Sample details	Sample no.	Starting moisture content (%)	C_u kg/cm^2	E^* kg/cm^2	Failure e_f (%)	$e_{0.48}$	Moisture content (%) at the test time	Dry density g/cc
Purulia soil (blank)	S-001	41.3	0.076	2.45	17.6	1.01	33.7	1.350
	S-002	46.4	0.077	2.98	17.0	0.95	33.8	1.397
	S-003	46.4	0.074	2.74	17.0	0.95	33.8	1.397
Purulia soil + 0.2% Ca^{2+} ($CaCl_2$)	S-111	44.0	0.112	2.95	15.4	0.91	32.3	1.426
Purulia soil + 0.4% Ca^{2+} ($CaCl_2$)	S-121	43.1	0.091	2.47	16.5	0.90	32.8	1.428
Purulia soil + 1% Ca^{2+} ($CaCl_2$)	S-131	42.4	0.078	7.80	8.8	0.93	33.0	1.412
Purulia soil + 0.2% Ca^{2+} [$Ca(OH)_2$]	S-311	46.0	0.069	1.89	19.7	0.98	33.3	1.373
Purulia soil + 0.4% Ca^{2+} [$Ca(OH)_2$]	S-321	46.9	0.071	2.04	19.9	1.01	35.0	1.354
Purulia soil + 1% Ca^{2+} [$Ca(OH)_2$]	S-331	44.3	0.074	2.63	18.5	1.02	34.0	1.347

* Except Purulia soil all other data of stabilized soil are average of different specimens.

Secant modulus at 1/2 the failure load. S Stands for shear test of sediment soil.

positive correlation has been found with the tests done in this test programme.

Shear test :

The results of the unconfined shear tests have been given in Table 8. Fig. 6 presents some typical stress-strain plots.

Any change in soil-water system which reduces double layer thickness tends to increase the shear strength of the soil (at a given void ratio), as interaction of the lowered double layers of two adjacent colloids results in decrease of interparticle repulsion. The factors that control the increase in shear strength of clay are : (i) increase of electrolyte concentration, (ii) cation exchange from low to high valence, (iii) decrease of pH of the pore fluid, (iv) decrease in water content etc.

In the sedimented soils mixed with chemical additives, the general tendency of additives is causing an increase in shear strength. The undrained shear strength of the original soil has been found to be 0.076 kg/cm², while the values of C_u of the stabilized soils have been found to range from 0.069 to 0.112 kg/cm². But the secant modulus values of the stabilized soils are 1.89 to 7.80 kg/cm² in contrast with the value of the blank soil 3.23 kg/cm². So the stabilized soils are stronger but of fluctuating stiffness, so far as this set of test is concerned. The failure strains are more or less similar excepting very low values for the samples S-131, S-431 and S-521. The void ratios of the sedimented soils i.e. the e_{0.48} values are more or less similar to the e_{0.48} values computed from the e – log p curves of the consolidation test done on the same samples indicating that in the sedimentation tank sedimentation in 48 h is sufficient to dissipate almost completely the pore water pressure due to surcharge weight.

With addition of CaCl₂ strength has been increased but astonishingly with Ca(OH)₂ additive, increment in shear strength is not clear. Of course, the dry density of the sedimented stabilized soil with Ca(OH)₂ is rather less compared to the blank soil, moulding moisture being higher than the moisture of other stabilized soils.

The addition of salt causes double layer depression and the value of liquid limit make soil denser and of higher strength after sedimentation. In case of Ca(OH)₂ added soil the cementing effect obtained in the compacted soil has been found to be absent in the sedimented soil possibly due to the fact that the hydrated forms of the cementing agents are not so effective in creating cementation bonds. Increase in electrolyte concentration and increase in pH have opposing effects in case of Ca(OH)₂ treated soils.

The stronger stabilized soils have higher density meaning more number of typical bonds among the particles but the chemical additives possibly contribute marginally to the cementation bond which is mobilised after much deformation caused on the soil samples. This marginal bond may also contribute to the lower initial value of C_c (compression index) of the stabilized soils (stage-1).

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